

Assessing Subjective Probabilistic Expectations in Household Surveys with Audio Records*

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Abstract

Probabilistic questions about future income or housing price are increasingly used in household surveys. However, there is still much to learn about the elicitation process itself. Do households fully understand this kind of questions? Do interviewers comply with those protocols that are intended to standardize the interview and minimize potential biases during the expectations elicitation process in F2F contexts? One interesting source of information to shed light on all these questions is provided by audio records. In this paper, we develop a state-of-the-art audio transcription machine learning pipeline to process audios recorded in the Spanish Survey of Household Finances (EFF) for a subjective probabilistic expectations question on housing prices. From these transcriptions, we compute meaningful measures of the incidence of interviewers' compliance with protocols and respondents' difficulties when answering this question. Our results show that the incidence of deviations from protocols such as the verbatim reading of questions and non-neutral probing is non-negligible. Besides, the incidence of respondents asking for clarifications or being reminded that points should be add up to ten is also high. In addition to the heterogeneity of these measures by households and interviewers' characteristics, we also document how they are associated to different measures of future house prices uncertainty observed in households' responses. In particular, speech rate, verbatim reading and non-neutral probing seem to be strongly correlated to the incidence of uncertainty.

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1 Introduction

Individuals' expectations about future events or outcomes play a fundamental role in explaining their decisions. In the last decades, economic theory models have relaxed strong assumptions such as rational expectations to consider that economic agents form expectations as subjective probabilistic distributions. Since the seminal work of [Manski \(2004\)](#), questions eliciting individuals and households' subjective probabilistic expectations have been included in many individual and household surveys such as the Health and Retirement Study (HRS), the Survey of Health, Aging and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), the Survey of Consumer Finances (SCF), the Household Finance and Consumption Survey (HFCS) or the Survey of Financial Competences (ECF by its Spanish Acronym). Besides, there is an already extensive existing literature that has documented their consistency and predictive power. In this sense, survey-based elicited expectations have turned out to be very useful for fiscal and monetary policy-makers ([Weber et al., 2022](#); [D'Acunto and Weber, 2024](#)). However, asking for probabilities or probability distributions is not an easy task so that we need to better understand about its elicitation process. Regarding this, random survey-based experiments comparing different settings or formulations of a given expectations question have been used as an evaluation tool. These experiments have provided evidence of different key aspects when eliciting subjective probabilistic expectations, such as the question wording ([Bruine de Bruin et al., 2017, 2012](#)), the support in the form of visual aid ([Delavande et al., 2010](#); [Delavande and Rohwedder, 2008](#)) or the interview mode ([Bruine de Bruin et al., 2017](#)). Other articles have studied forms of rounding that may bias the measurement of expectations ([Manski et al., 2010](#); [Binder et al., 2023](#)) or the panel conditioning effect ([Kim and Binder, 2023](#)) (for a detailed review of recent advances, see [Bruine de Bruin et al. \(2023\)](#)). Overall, while progress has been made, there is still much to learn about the elicitation process itself and how respondents' react when being asked this type of question. Indeed, economists are increasingly interested in understanding people's reasoning when thinking about beliefs and expectations. Some have used novel techniques based on text data from open-ended questions to measure what are the roots of individuals' beliefs and motivations ([Haaland et al., 2024](#); [Galasso et al., 2024](#)). In this context, the use of *paradata* - i.e., generated data during the

interview, such as audios recorded from the conversation or duration times - might represent a very unique and informative resource to learn more about the process of answering and about potential biases and measurement errors (Olson and Parkhurst, 2013; Yan and Olson, 2013; Couper and Kreuter, 2013). In addition, audio records can be collected massively, for all respondents, providing information for a whole sample representative of the population. This is an important advantage over cognitive interviews, which are conducted for a small number of individuals*.

Regarding the interviewing mode, one crucial point that deserves special attention in face-to-face settings is how interviewers can influence respondents' responses, i.e., the so-called interviewer effect (Kish, 1962; Mangione et al., 1992; Ongena and Dijkstra, 2007; Vandenplas et al., 2017). One way to minimize such effects is done by the standardization of interviewing protocols referring to the interaction with the respondent, the reading of the questions, their probing behavior or their explanations to respondents about the survey and interview procedures (Fowler and Mangione, 1990). Audio records can also help to elucidate on to what extent interviewers comply with this standardization. Indeed, audio records have been used to measure response times, speech rate, pitch or pausing with the aim of gaining insights about interviewers and interviewees' reactions and interactions (Conrad et al., 2013; Bergmann and Bristle, 2020; Benkí et al., 2011) but for questions or context different from those of probabilistic subjective expectations (Schaeffer et al., 2008).

This paper follows these lines to investigate the use of unstructured data such as audio records to gain insights about the measurement of subjective probabilistic expectations. Using data from the Spanish Survey of Household Finances (EFF by its Spanish acronym), we develop a state-of-the-art machine learning pipeline to process massively audios recorded for a subjective probabilistic expectations item, specifically, a question that asks households

*For example, the Federal Reserve Bank of New York conducted cognitive interviews during the six year-development and testing period of their Survey of Consumer Expectations to assess how people understand qualitative expectations questions on inflation. In particular, they asked people to think out loud while answering the Michigan Survey of Consumers' qualitative expectations question about inflation: "During the next 12 months, do you think prices in general will go up, go down, or stay where they are now?" Participants who reported that prices would go up or down were then asked by what percent they thought prices would change. Feedback from the respondents showed that some interpreted the question as asking about inflation, whereas others interpreted it as asking about the prices they pay (Armantier et al., 2013). Although useful, such cognitive interviews lack population representativeness, given that they are conducted on a small number of individuals.

about future home prices changes. From audio records, we extract information that measures multiple question-answering features. First, we extract specific indicators about how interviewers comply with protocols (e.g. reading verbatim or the use of the visual aid) or their probing behavior. Second, we define specific indicators about how respondents react to the questions (e.g. whether they express out loud doubt or not, they ask for additional clarifications or need to be reminded the number of points they should distribute across different scenarios).

Our results show that the incidence of deviations from protocols such as the verbatim reading of questions and non-neutral probing is non-negligible. Besides, the incidence of respondents asking for clarifications or being reminded that points should be add up to ten is also high. We also document the heterogeneity of these measures by demographic groups (e.g. the age and education level of the respondent seem to be particularly important). We ask also whether these audio characteristics are associated to the bunching observed in the EFF data. In particular, speech rate, verbatim reading and non-neutral probing seem to have substantial effect on the incidence of those responses.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first paper that proposes and uses audio records to gather and process relevant information about how interviewers and respondents interact when answering probabilistic expectations questions. In this sense, our paper provides new evidence on the elicitation process of subjective probabilistic expectations based on novel data sources to both the economics and survey methodology literatures.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a brief review of the related literature. In Section 3 we describe the EFF and the specific subjective expectation question of interest. In Section 4 we provide details on the audio records used, the transcription methods developed and implemented and the specific measures extracted from the processed data. In Section 5 we validate the machine learning output with human annotations. Section 6 contains our results and main findings. Finally, we suggest some further directions to be explored in future research in the final Section 7.

2 Related Literature

This paper is related to the intersection between economics and survey methodology. Regarding economics, there is a growing interest in improving the understanding on how people allocate attention to take simple decisions (Gabaix, 2019) or the narratives that people use to explain economic phenomena (Andre et al., 2022). A few experiments have been made using audio records to study the process of verbal transmission distortions and economic information (Graeber et al., 2024b,a). A recent survey by Haaland et al. (2024) relates all recent efforts in measuring how people think, by reviewing research that relies mostly on open-ended questions. In fact, Galasso et al. (2024) conclude that oral responses, although longer, possess a simpler lexical structure. Their analysis suggests that in open-ended questions overall informational content is greater than written responses. Our present study could be viewed as such since the interviewer-household speech sequence - the conversation - is open-ended in nature.

Besides, this work is related to the household expectations' literature, as measured from survey data. Studies like those of Weber et al. (2022); D'Acunto and Weber (2024) highlight the importance of survey-based economic expectations data for economics research and the need to understand the elicitation process. In this sense, several studies have focused on the quantification of various sources of measurement error or variation during the elicitation process, such as the impact of different wording (Bruine de Bruin et al., 2017, 2012), rounding effect (Manski et al., 2010), visual aids (Delavande et al., 2010) or the learning-by-doing effect (Binder et al., 2023). However, with the exception of Graeber et al. (2024b), these studies do not analyze how variation in the transmitter of information (orator, or in our case, interviewer) contributes to the expectations formation. As such, this study addresses several key aspects of survey research. First, it examines coding schemes for question-answering sequences. Ongena (2005) work provides a foundational nomenclature for coding and characterizing phenomena within question-answering sequences, including interviewers' literal reading of questions. We follow the deductive coding scheme framework of Haaland et al. (2024) for hypothesis testing. Related to coding schemes are the speech-based variables to analyze different dimensions of a conversation. Regarding the literal reading of the question

and protocol compliance of protocols, [Bergmann and Bristle \(2020\)](#) found that reading times decreased over a survey's field period, influencing respondent behavior based on the question wording's relevant information. [Smit et al. \(1997\)](#) studied suggestive probing through a field experiment, finding that it affects data quality, and [Ackermann-Piek and Massing \(2015\)](#) emphasized the importance of interviewer training before conducting surveys.

The present study uses a machine learning pipeline to detect probing behavior, specifically induced bunching, where households allocate all points of the subjective expectation distribution into a single slot. Interviewer fluency and speech rate are also examined. Several studies ([Schaeffer et al., 2008](#); [Couper and Kreuter, 2013](#); [Vandenplas et al., 2019](#)) show that interviewer effects are more frequent in fast and slow-paced interviews, with deviations from moderate speed resulting in lower data quality. [Olson et al. \(2019\)](#) found that question characteristics affect reading behavior and administration time, with non-protocol questions taking longer and being read faster. [Benkí et al. \(2011\)](#) demonstrated that moderate speech rate (3.5 words/sec) and neither completely fluent nor disfluent pausing schemes led to highest participation rates in telephone surveys. This paper considers also the speech rate as a variable to analyze. Response latency, as discussed by [Draisma and Dijkstra \(2004\)](#), reflects the processing time needed to answer a question and is connected to paralinguistic indicators and response errors. In our study we also calculate cognitive-related household characteristics, such as silence duration and instances of households not knowing what to say.

By the processing of audio records from advanced analytical techniques, this research builds upon and extends all this previous work in survey methodology, offering new insights into interviewer-respondent interactions and how this can be associated to variation in elicited subjective probabilistic expectations.

3 Data, Questions and Formulations

We use data from wave 2020 and 2022 of the Spanish Survey of Household Finances. The EFF is a longitudinal survey conducted by Banco de España (BdE hereafter) since 2002 to

provide detailed information on households' assets, debt, income and spending. The population frame for the EFF sample is the Spanish Population Register. Also, the wealth tax file information from individual wealth tax returns, held by Spanish tax agency, serves as the oversampling basis for wealthy households. The majority of questions refer to the household as a whole except for labor and related income that are collected for each household member over the age of 16. Most of the information makes reference to the time of the interview, although information on all pre-tax income sources is also referring to the previous calendar year. The information is collected through personal interviews with households, conducted by interviewers with specific training and computer-assisted (CAPI). In 2020, due to the pandemic context, interviews were conducted by telephone (CATI). The final sample usually consists of around 6300 households, 50% having participated in other EFF waves (panel component), with an oversampling of wealthy individuals of around 12% for the top 1% of the wealth distribution. The average response rate is about 40% for the non-panel component and 75% for the panel component. For a detailed overview of the survey characteristics, such as response rates, samples sizes, and other EFF the methodological document of [Barceló et al. \(2020\)](#). To ensure accuracy and internal consistency of the data, BdE and the survey agency conduct strict monitoring and quality procedures such as the case-by-case revision of all interviews completed to detect deviations, omissions or mistakes. Households are even re-contacting, under some circumstances, if clarifications are needed on their reported answers. In this context, audio records have become a crucial tool for the monitoring of interviewers' compliance. Reviewers from both the BdE and the survey agency listen all of them for each interview during their case-by-case revision.

Besides questions on assets, debts, incomes and spendings, the EFF asks respondents a question to elicit household house price probabilistic expectations. This question was introduced in the EFF in 2011 and started to be recorded in 2020. Following the so-called [Manski \(2004\)](#) format, households are asked to distribute ten points among five different scenarios concerning the price change of their homes over the next 12 months. Therefore, respondents are supposed to provide probabilities they assign to different future outcomes. This is a relevant question in the Spanish context because of the high concentration (80%) of household

wealth in real estate assets in Spain[†].

As of the 2020 and 2022 EFF waves, the question itself is formulated as follows:

We are interested in knowing how you think the price of your home will evolve in the next 12 months: distribute ten points among the following five possibilities, assigning more points to the scenarios you think are more likely (assign 0 if a scenario looks impossible):

- *Drop over 6 %*
- *Drop in between 2% and 6%*
- *Approximately stable (drops or increases of no more than 2%)*
- *Increase in between 2% and 6%*
- *Increase larger than 6 %*
- *Don't know*
- *No answer*

The question refers to the household main residence and is prompted for all households, regardless of their home ownership regime. Besides, it comes after having asked household respondents the whole sequence of questions on their main residence (e.g. the year of acquisition, the value when they acquired it and the question on its current value). In addition to the specific formulation used, interviewers and respondents need to follow standardized protocols and methods to minimize interviewer effects or systematic biases in the elicitation of probabilistic expectations questions. In particular, interviewers are instructed to read literally the statement of the question as it appears in the screen. Then, the respondent is handed out a showcard containing the question and the response options on which he/she could draft their answers. Explanations are provided by the interviewer if needed using the clarifications stated in the screen right below the main formulations. In addition, interviewers are instructed to read again the question if the respondent did not understand or could not follow the whole explanation. After the respondent has written down the answers in the paper, the interviewer has to insert the response reported into the computer and check that all ten points have been distributed. Finally, an automatic prompt appears on the screen if the answers entered in the computer by the interviewers do not add up to ten. In such cases,

[†]For more information regarding the wealth composition in Spain, please consult the EFF main figures [web-site](#)

the household respondent and the interviewer are asked to revise the answers. For a more detailed overview of the question and the 2011 wave descriptives, see [Bover \(2015\)](#). For basic descriptives of the 2020 and 2022 waves in our sample, see [Table 1](#). Also, [Table 7](#) in the

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of DK/NA

Variables	Observations		DK/NA (%)	
	2020	2022	2020	2022
Female	2280	2395	3.64	6.56
Male	3490	3300	2.21	3.76
Primary	773	673	7.12	13.08
Secondary	2048	2076	2.69	5.64
Tertiary	2910	2919	1.48	2.43
Under 35	311	367	2.25	5.45
35-45	986	925	1.12	2.81
46-55	1299	1358	1.54	3.98
56-65	1329	1342	1.88	3.80
66-75	1022	926	3.33	5.62
Over 75	823	777	7.65	10.04
Non-owner occupiers	1104	1262	4.62	8.08
Owner occupiers	4666	4433	2.34	4.04
Sample	5770	5695	2.77	4.93

Notes: Household sample statistics for EFF2020 and EFF2022. Sample is restricted to those accepting audio recording.

Appendix contains the same statistics for the whole population surveyed in both waves. As it is expected, since no big number of observations is lost, the results are quite similar.

4 Sample and Methods

4.1 Sample

Out of the 6,313 households interviewed in the 2020 wave, 411 did not agree to be recorded. In addition, another 132 observations were lost in the execution of the pipeline. For the 2022 wave, 6,385 households were interviewed, but 553 did not accept to be recorded and 137 observations were lost in the pipeline. Therefore, our final sample consists of 11,465 audios, of which 5,770 come from the 2020 wave and 5,695 from 2022. [Table 2](#) shows that audios from 2020 have an average duration of 75.11 seconds, whereas those for year 2022 last 70.23 seconds on average. Other descriptives look similar between both waves.

Table 2: Summary statistics of audios length (in seconds) in our sample

	N	Mean	Median	Max	Min	p_25	p_75
EFF 2020	5770	75.09	66.52	262.10	6.00	50.28	91.89
EFF 2022	5695	70.16	62.50	302.60	7.20	47.56	84.36

4.2 Machine Learning Pipeline

To construct audio characteristics, firstly data cleaning was conducted. Initially, a preprocessing step was undertaken to eliminate audios smaller than 15,000 bytes and bigger than 790,000 bytes which corresponds to audios bigger than a few seconds and smaller than around 7 minutes. This pruning of very small and very big audios is what makes some of the audios to fall. Additionally, the presence of background noise in recordings posed a challenge to transcription and voice activity detection performance. Therefore, a speech enhancement model was applied following the methodology of [Defossez et al. \(2020\)](#). This way, we removed several background noises and room reverb. We call this the filtered audios dataset, since the waveform is "filtered" according to the signal processing literature. However, it is important to note that filtering audio carries a risk of information loss, particularly in instances where reduced volume segments are removed. To mitigate this risk, both filtered and unfiltered audio recordings were retained. We finally obtained the transcriptions and voice activity detection timestamps of both datasets. But to construct the extracted audio characteristics, we used the resulting transcription (and its voice activity detection output) from the audio that produced the longest transcription among the filtered and unfiltered versions (with some caveats that are explained in Section 4.2.1). For a major overview of the pipeline, consult Figure B.1 in the Appendix. All models employed above were executed within a Python 3.9 local environment for confidentiality purposes, with a 10Gb RAM GPU.

4.2.1 Audio Transcription

The transcription has been performed using the *Whisper-large-v3* (Whisper from now on) model ([Radford et al., 2022](#)). As it is stated in the model card available at the HuggingFace platform[‡]: "*Whisper is a Transformer based encoder-decoder model, also referred to as a sequence-*

[‡][Whisper large-v3 card at HuggingFace](#)

to-sequence model. It was trained on 1 million hours of weakly labeled audio and 4 million hours of pseudolabeled audio collected using Whisper large-v2". In other words, Whisper is an open source pre-trained speech-to-text AI model. It has the same architecture as its smaller siblings but has a better performance over a variety of languages (10% to 20% reduction of errors compared to Whisper large-v2). Fortunately for us, Spanish is one of the languages with the most hours of training, which makes the transcription performance level one of the most robust in a wide variety of evaluation datasets. In particular by reaching Word Error Rate (WER) levels for Whisper large-v2 of 4.2% on Multilingual LibriSpeech, 5,6% on Common Voice or 8,2% on VoxPopuli (for more details see [Radford et al. \(2022\)](#))[§]. As can be seen in the Section 5.1 for our case we do not obtain such good results in terms of WER. This can be explained by the fact that the training audio corpus of the Whisper models rarely deals with overspeech and further research is still needed in this direction (see [Shen et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Meng et al. \(2023\)](#) for the latest advances on this topic).

In their basic form, Whisper models cannot work with audios longer than 30 seconds (they are trained with this amount), which hinders their use in real-life applications, as is our case, since the average duration of our recordings is around 75 seconds in 2020 wave and 70 seconds in 2022 wave. However, using a chunking algorithm deployed by [Gandhi et al. \(2023\)](#) and proposed by [Patry \(2022\)](#), it is possible to obtain transcriptions of audios of a long duration. This chunking algorithm breaks the long audio file into smaller segments overlapping slightly with the adjoining fragments. Moreover, hallucinations are common in the transcription of long-form audios containing a higher proportion of non-vocal interventions ([Koenecke et al. \(2024\)](#)). That is, the model will output a transcript unrelated with the audio (especially repeated words, numbers or sentences). In order to mitigate this problem, a large number of tests were performed with different configurations. We found that the chunk length parameter affected the appearance of hallucinations. We set such value as 20 seconds. In addition, we observed that by setting the model to return sentence level timestamps and giving it some context of the previous and next chunk (`stride.length_s = (4,2)` which indicates the length in seconds of stride on the left and right of each chunk) the quality of the

[§]At the time of publishing this document, whisper large-v3 results were not yet available

transcript improved.

Once we have the transcriptions of both the filtered and the original audios, we compare their lengths and check for the presence of hallucinations. We perform such task with a sequence of rules. If the longest transcript does not contain hallucinations, we keep it. If not, we check if the other (albeit shorter) transcript has hallucinations. If it does not, we keep such shorter transcription. If it does contain hallucinations, we would re-transcribe these audios with a new configuration (new value for chunk length). Once re-transcribed, we would go through the same process, applying the same strategy to decide which transcript to keep, until no hallucinations are detected. To detect hallucinations, we relied on a simple rule: transcription that entail a repeated word 50 times is considered an hallucination.

4.2.2 Speaker Diarization

Speaker diarization involves partitioning an audio stream containing human speech into homogeneous segments that differentiate between the utterances of distinct speakers. To carry it out we have used the Pyannote package developed by [Plaquet and Bredin \(2023\)](#) and [Bredin \(2023\)](#). It is an open-source toolkit written in Python for speaker diarization. This package contains pre-trained models for different tasks such as voice activity detection, speaker change detection, overlapped speech detection and speaker embedding. In addition, it allows the user to combine the different results of each of these models to create a speaker diarization pipeline. Our initial aim was to detect both interviewer and household voices, using a speaker diarization model so that we could add this information when detecting the different regular expressions. In the different tests we performed, we observed a diarization error rate that was in line with the results obtained for this metric in the original paper by [Plaquet and Bredin \(2023\)](#) (see [Figure 4](#) and [Figure 5](#) in Appendix for an example). Despite this, we consider that the distinction between interviewer and interviewee in the transcription output attending to diarization results would be adding more error in the variable creation step. For that reason, we only use the voice activity detection (VAD) model from this library. A VAD model is able to precisely distinguish a human voice from other kind of sound. This will result in a fine characterization of silence (no speaking) parts of the

conversation between the household and the interviewer. Furthermore, the Pyannote VAD model achieves state-of-the-art performance on this task (Bredin et al. (2019)). We use the default hyperparameters from Bain et al. (2023), as we do not have labeled data available for fine-tuning.

4.3 Audio Extracted Characteristics

Finally, we construct eight audio characteristics. These characteristics refer to the interviewer probing behavior, her compliance with standardized protocols, and specific aspects related to the cognitive process undertaken by households when answering the question. All variables except three are constructed by searching for regular expressions in the transcribed text. Additionally, other two are based also on the transcript. Hence, the transcription is the centerpiece for extracting the relevant information used in the analysis.

Regarding interviewer’s compliance with protocols we extract four indicators. First, an indicator (1) for whether the interviewer formulates literally the question (even if there is an interruption). This is of great interest to the survey methodology literature interested in how deviations from guidelines affect survey answers (see Bergmann and Bristle (2020), Ackermann-Piek and Massing (2015) or Haan et al. (2013)). For that purpose, we compute a semantic similarity metric using a Sentence-Transformer model (Cañete et al., 2020). This Natural Language Processing pre-trained model is able to capture the semantic meaning of language for multiple languages. In our case, we use it to compare the question’s verbatim text and the transcribed text of the first 30 seconds of the audio. We set this 30-second threshold because we consider it sufficient time for the interviewer to read the question. By encoding such first part of the transcription, we obtain a numerical representation that takes into account the context and meaning of what the interviewer literally said. Thus, comparing such encoding with the literal question gives us a representation of whether the interviewer is complying with this protocol. We use the cosine similarity metric to calculate such comparison, which is bounded between -1 and 1. The higher the score, the greater the semantic similarity between the two texts. Second (2), we compute a binary indicator for whether the showcard is mentioned in the conversation by means of regular expressions.

The showcard should always be used to help respondent visualize all the answer options. To compute whether the interviewer is showing such showcard or not, we look for the Spanish transcription of expression ‘Showcard’[¶]. Third (3), we compute a binary indicator that stands for whether the interviewer reminds the household that total points should add up to ten. To do so, we look for the Spanish transcription of expressions “Sum to 10” and “Total 10”. Finally, the fourth (4) indicator measures the speech rate, which is computed considering the total length of the whole interaction between the respondent and the interviewer. In particular, it is calculated as the number of words in the transcribed text divided by the total time that is registered in the paradata of the audio. [Benkí et al. \(2011\)](#) and [Conrad et al. \(2013\)](#) among other have studied the effect of the speech rate on the success of survey invitations, but there is no evidence about the effect of speech rate on the answers of probabilistic subjective questions.

Regarding non-neutral probing, we compute a binary variable (5) that indicates whether the interviewer probes a one option answer by the respondent in the following way: “so then, shall we put the ten points to that option?” instead of “so then, how many points do you assign to that option? Any other else?”. With the help of the survey team we came up with a pattern that is common in this type of behaviors. The specific form of this pattern can be seen in the Section [C](#) of the Appendix.

Finally, we construct several measures related to the respondents’ reactions during the exercise. First, we compute a binary indicator (6) for whether the household verbalizes that does not understand the exercise. This might also lead the interviewer to give additional explanations. In particular, we look for expressions such as: “I don’t understand”. Second, (7) we consider an alternative binary indicator for whether the household is expressing doubts during the conversation or throughout the resolution of the exercise. To do so, we look for expressions such as “I don’t know” or “I have no idea”. As demonstrated by [Draisma and Dijkstra \(2004\)](#), there is a connection between some paralinguistic indicators as doubt words and measurement error. We firmly believe that by looking for these expressions we will capture household behaviours because based on our experience it is very rare to find situations

[¶]In Spanish the word card is accentuated but we also search for the word without accent

where the interviewer makes such comments. For a more detailed explanation of the regular expressions used and the explanation of the variables, see Section C in the Appendix. Third, the total duration time in seconds of silence in the conversation (8). This is obtained by adding up the duration in seconds of all those regions where the VAD algorithm does not detect any sound activity.

One limitation of the indicators based on regular expressions extracted from the audio transcriptions is that they probably might not capture fully the patterns of interest since there might be other ways those patterns can happen. For instance in the case of the variable capturing the use of the showcard, the interviewer could leave the showcard on the table for the household to read it without the need of mentioning the word "showcard" out loud. Thus, we consider these extracted indicators as measures of audio characteristics with some measurement error. Still, we think that they contain valuable information of the phenomena of interest.

5 Validation of Output

In this section we provide several validation exercises of the output we have generated from the audios: the transcriptions of audios, the VAD algorithm and the extracted binary audio indicators. This validation consists basically in comparing on a random sample of 120 audios, 60 for each wave, the automatically generated transcriptions, voice activity timestamps and binary indicators with the manually computed versions of those, which are considered as the benchmark. These validation exercises were conducted with the assistance of a graduate student. In particular, she executed manually the transcription of the audios for this small sample and computed the five binary variables based on regular expressions explained in Section 4.3.

5.1 Whisper Validation

The automatically generated transcriptions of audio records were compared with our benchmark using a metric: the word error rate (WER). This metric is defined as:

$$\text{word error rate} = \frac{S + D + I}{S + D + C} \quad (1)$$

where S is the number of substitutions, D is the number of deletions, I is the number of insertions and C is the number of correct words, which are defined when confronting the automatic transcription against the manual one. We opt to use the WER because it is the most widely used metric in speech recognition articles (see [Radford et al. \(2022\)](#), [Zhang et al. \(2022\)](#) or [Wang et al. \(2021\)](#)). However, it has some limitations. [Radford et al. \(2022\)](#) highlights that due to the fact that WER is based on string edit distance, it can penalize transcripts of non-semantic differences. This is not as common in Spanish as it is in English because we do not have contractions. But for our particular case, numerical and percentage expressions are very common and a possible source of errors. So before testing the validity of the output that we have obtained from the transcription pipeline, we standardize both outputs following the basic normalizer established in [Radford et al. \(2022\)](#):

1. Remove any phrases between matching brackets ([,]).
2. Remove any phrases between matching parentheses ((,)).
3. Replace any markers, symbols, and punctuation characters with a space, i.e. when the Unicode category of each character in the NFKC-normalized string starts with M, S, or P.
4. Make the text lowercase.
5. Replace any successive whitespace characters with a space.

For our particular task, we have added two other standardization rules:

6. Replace percentage symbols (%) with the Spanish word for "percent".
7. Replace digits with their word representation.

After normalization we have calculated the WER for the 2020 and 2022 waves. In the first case we have obtained a WER of 24.19% and for the next wave under study a WER of 24.86%. This measure may seem a little high in relation to the results obtained by [Radford et al. \(2022\)](#), although this comparison is not fair because our audios are way noisier than the ones used

in [Radford et al. \(2022\)](#). To make sure that we can continue our exercise, we have obtained the words in which the model makes the most errors in this small sample under study. As can be seen in [Figure 1](#), these are words such as articles, conjunctions or nouns that are not important in our regular expressions. Special attention should be paid to [Figure 1\(a\)](#) and [Figure 1\(b\)](#) which include the words that the model transcription is not able to capture, i.e. words that the model does not transcribe but are present in the manual transcription and the additional words that the model transcription contains but are not present in the manual transcription. A closer look at these figures shows that there is no combination of these words in which systematic errors are made that could affect our regular expression search. Therefore, we consider that the quality of the transcription is sufficient to be able to continue with the exercise.

Figure 1: Frequency of Word Deletions, Insertions, and Substitutions in the Manually Transcribed Audios

(a) Frequency of Deletions

(b) Frequency of Insertions

(c) Frequency of Substitutions

Notes: Figure shows the top 30 words that are most frequently deleted, inserted, and substituted in the 120 audio sample used to validate Whisper’s transcriptions.

5.2 VAD Validation

To validate the VAD algorithm, the audios of the random sample taken to validate the transcription algorithm were also manually annotated. This work was carried out by one of the team members using audio annotation software. The audios have been annotated with the idea of marking as active audio regions all those moments in which the voice of one of the participants is recorded (even when there are moments of active silence: when interviewer fillers (e.g., ‘um’, ‘uh’...) and householders’ backchannels (e.g., ‘uh huh’, ‘I see’...) appear).

Then these results have been compared with the output of the VAD algorithm of these same audios in order to compute a Detection Error Rate (DER) metric. DER is defined as¹¹:

$$\text{Detection Error Rate} = \frac{\text{False Alarm} + \text{Missed Detection}}{\text{Total}} \quad (2)$$

where false alarm is the duration of non-speech incorrectly classified as speech, missed detection is the duration of speech incorrectly classified as non-speech, and total is the total duration of speech in the reference. We have obtained a DER of 13.83% for 2020 audios and 12.70% for 2022 audios. It must be said that these results may be inflated since the VAD algorithm can mark as active audio regions moments in which some sufficiently loud background noise is heard (this sensitivity of the algorithm to detect noise can be controlled by means of the algorithm configuration). For that reason, it is plausible that the results obtained can be seen as an upper bound with the algorithm's errors actually being lower.

5.3 Binary Audio Features Validation

To assess the quality of the extracted indicators based on text expressions a manual annotation exercise has been performed. The results obtained manually by a graduate student were compared with the results obtained computationally by our pipeline following a similar strategy to [Graeber et al. \(2024b\)](#) using Cohen's κ ([Cohen \(1960\)](#)). In their study they perform two exercises. First, they determine the quality of the annotation made by one human of a particular task with the annotation of that same task made by another human. And second, they use GPT-4 to perform the annotation and again compare it with the original human annotation. In our case, we simply test whether the human annotator finds the same behaviors we are trying to capture with the proposed regular expressions. It is important to note that the human annotator was not instructed to identify the expressions we defined since it was blind to the patterns proposed. But it was instructed to capture the behavior we were looking for even if they occurred in ways different from what we had defined.

For the indicator measuring the use of the showcard, the instruction given to the coder was

¹¹ [Pyannote.metrics official documentation](#)

to code 1 if the card was mentioned in any way in the audio (e.g., instead of directly mentioning the card the interviewer can verbally or not verbally signal to the interviewee that there is help available). In that sense, the probability of both raters systems agreed is 89%, reaching a Cohen's κ value of 0.55, indicating "moderate agreement" (Landis and Koch (1977)). For the variable that captures whether the interviewer reminds the household that the exercise should add up to ten points, the coder was instructed to code 1 if from the audio it was clear that the respondent was reminded in any way that the total should be ten. For this variable we get that in 92% of the cases both raters identify the same behaviour. Cohen's κ is 0.73, indicating "substantial" agreement. For the variable that captures if the respondent expressed some doubts, the instruction given to the coder was to code 1 in case the interviewee verbalises that she does not know how it is going to evolve her household price. Thus, we obtained that both coding systems agreed in 88% of the cases, reaching a Cohen κ of 0.62%, showing "substantial" agreement. For the variable that captures if there have been lack of understanding in the interaction, the instruction given to the coder was to code 1 if the interviewee expresses that she does not understand the exercise. In this regard, the human annotation and the computational annotation agreed in 97% of the cases, what means a Cohen's κ of 0.49% indicating "moderate" agreement. The problem in this case is that in our small sample only 2 observations presented lack of understanding as qualified by the computing annotation. Hence this imbalance of classes generates such a high percentage of agreement. Finally, for the variable capturing non-neutral probing, we have asked the coder to note this behavior as present if the interviewer guides the interviewee's response in a non-neutral way and does not let her make a free choice so the interviewee ended up assigning all ten points to a single category. Resulting in an agreement rate between coding systems of 89% and a Cohen's κ of 0.65% indicating "substantial" agreement.

6 Results

6.1 Descriptive Analysis

6.1.1 Audio Measures

Tables 3 and 4 show sample means for all the indicators constructed from audio records collected for the last two available editions of the survey (2020 and 2022). They also provide some breakdown by respondents' demographic characteristics (such as the gender, the age, and the level of education of the respondents, plus the households' property regime of their main residence as a proxy of household wealth).

Table 3: Means of binary audio indicators by respondents' characteristics

Variables	Observations		Reminder sums 10 (%)		Int. shows card 10 (%)		Doubt (%)		Lack of Understanding (%)		Induce (%)	
	2020	2022	2020	2022	2020	2022	2020	2022	2020	2022	2020	2022
Female	2280	2395	11.14	13.24	90.04	79.00	23.51	25.76	2.46	2.38	8.42	6.47
Male	3490	3300	8.97	12.64	89.97	80.27	13.18	15.39	0.89	1.21	6.42	5.91
Primary	773	673	7.63	8.17	87.06	73.70	25.87	30.46	3.75	3.27	9.18	8.32
Secondary	2048	2076	9.81	12.72	90.48	79.53	18.99	21.87	1.76	1.73	8.45	7.27
Tertiary	2910	2919	10.52	14.11	90.72	81.47	13.61	15.69	0.65	1.27	5.81	4.83
Under 35	311	367	10.93	16.62	87.78	80.65	17.04	13.08	2.25	1.36	7.07	4.36
35-45	986	925	11.87	12.97	90.67	80.54	13.69	17.08	0.91	1.62	5.48	4.86
46-55	1299	1358	9.85	12.89	91.15	80.04	14.32	18.11	1.15	1.55	6.54	5.60
56-65	1329	1342	9.63	11.03	90.97	80.77	18.21	19.75	1.58	1.49	6.55	5.44
66-75	1022	926	8.61	15.12	89.14	81.21	19.77	23.22	1.37	1.84	8.41	6.48
Over 75	823	777	8.75	11.58	87.73	74.26	21.63	24.84	2.55	2.45	9.96	10.30
Non-owner occupiers	1104	1262	9.87	12.04	91.58	81.38	20.38	22.58	2.36	2.61	7.61	5.94
Owner occupiers	4666	4433	9.82	13.13	89.63	79.27	16.52	18.95	1.31	1.44	7.12	6.20
Total	5770	5695	9.83	12.89	90.00	79.74	17.26	19.75	1.51	1.70	7.21	6.15

Notes: Multiple household characteristics are detailed for the audio extracted characteristics: sex, education, age and housing regime. Please consult subsection 4.3 for the measurement of the variables specified in all columns.

Results in Table 3 show that the incidence of the problems measured from our audio transcriptions is relatively high. For example, respondents are reminded that assigned points need to add up to 10 in a non-negligible number of cases (9.83% of the overall cases in 2020 and 12.89% in 2022, columns 4 and 5). The fact that this happened in a lower percentage of cases during the 2020 wave might be associated to the telephone mode used during the pandemic. The use of the telephone might force people to be more focused or concentrated in the exercise, decreasing the probability of being reminded about the 10 points. On the other hand, it seems also plausible that both respondents and interviewers are more prone to use the option of assigning the 10 points to just one scenario (the so-called bunching) while using the telephone **. Columns 6 and 7 show that the aid card was mentioned in 90% of the

**In fact, Table 5 below shows that the level of bunching is substantially higher for specific groups of respondents under the telephone mode

cases in 2020 and in around 80% in 2022. A similar gap is observed for all groups by the respondents' characteristics. Even though this might suggest that the showcard was not used in a substantial proportion of interviews, especially in 2022, this conclusion should be considered with caution since in F2F interviews interviewers might hand directly the showcard to the respondents without reading out loud the word "Showcard". This is an important caveat of this measure to monitor the compliance with this protocol. Results in columns 8 and 9 show that expressions meaning "Do not know" or alike are used in around 17-20% of cases. Besides, women express doubts more often than men on average. In particular, the gender gap in the prevalence of this behavior is of 10 pp. There is also a clear negative gradient by education level and a positive gradient by age which means that less educated respondents and older respondents are more likely to express doubts when being confronted to this question. These patterns are observed in both waves. Furthermore, respondents who do not own their main residence are also 4 pp more likely to express doubts than home owners. This seems to be related to the fact that renters might find more difficult to think about and provide an estimation of the value of the house they live in given that they cannot sell it. This finding is in line with the results of [Kiesl-Reiter et al. \(2024\)](#), who shows that those who own a house possess more accurate information regarding past house price changes. As for the 'lack of understanding' measure (columns 10-11), we observe analogous patterns to the doubting behaviour although in this case the incidence levels are very low. In particular, women, less educated and older respondents are more likely to express lack of understanding. Additionally, we find that lack of understanding is more prevalent in those respondents who are non-owner occupiers. As we mentioned earlier, renters might find more difficult providing an estimation on the price of their residence or they may even think that the question refers to the value of their rent. One important remark regarding the indicators for lack of understanding or doubts is that both measures are based on a specific fixed list of regular expressions or words, so that our results are conditional to the presence (or not) of those expressions. Finally, we find that the incidence of deviations from important protocols such as non-neutral probing is non-negligible (columns 12-13). In particular, this misbehaviour occurred in 7.21% of the cases in 2020 and 6.15% in 2022. By respondents' characteristics, our results show similar patterns to the two previous measures. For example, interviewers are

more likely to probe non-neutrally when interviewing respondents who are older and with a lower level of education. However, we do not observe differences by ownership status.

Table 4: Mean and standard deviations for continuous audio indicators by respondents' characteristics

Variables	Observations		Semantic score				Silent time (seconds)				Speech rate (words/sec)			
	2020	2022	2020		2022		2020		2022		2020		2022	
			μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Female	2280	2395	0.69	0.21	0.70	0.16	30.65	20.41	18.86	14.84	2.48	0.57	2.76	0.58
Male	3490	3300	0.69	0.21	0.71	0.15	29.72	19.32	17.93	13.72	2.38	0.56	2.70	0.57
Primary	773	673	0.65	0.23	0.67	0.18	30.51	19.41	18.22	13.99	2.47	0.53	2.82	0.63
Secondary	2048	2076	0.69	0.21	0.70	0.16	30.95	20.57	19.07	15.23	2.44	0.55	2.75	0.56
Tertiary	2910	2919	0.70	0.20	0.72	0.15	29.35	19.21	17.79	13.49	2.39	0.59	2.69	0.57
Under 35	311	367	0.71	0.20	0.73	0.12	32.39	19.86	19.48	14.14	2.42	0.84	2.69	0.58
35-45	986	925	0.72	0.19	0.72	0.15	30.95	20.63	19.53	14.80	2.44	0.59	2.71	0.57
46-55	1299	1358	0.71	0.20	0.71	0.15	29.57	18.77	19.07	15.81	2.41	0.54	2.73	0.58
56-65	1329	1342	0.70	0.20	0.71	0.15	29.45	19.12	17.53	13.07	2.42	0.51	2.75	0.59
66-75	1022	926	0.66	0.22	0.69	0.17	29.05	19.09	16.81	12.82	2.38	0.52	2.75	0.55
Over 75	823	777	0.64	0.23	0.67	0.18	31.32	21.82	18.16	13.83	2.43	0.60	2.70	0.56
Non-owner occupiers	1104	1262	0.69	0.20	0.70	0.16	33.72	21.22	19.33	14.48	2.42	0.66	2.72	0.58
Owner occupiers	4666	4433	0.69	0.21	0.71	0.16	29.23	19.30	18.03	14.12	2.42	0.54	2.73	0.57
Total	5770	5695	0.69	0.21	0.71	0.16	30.09	19.76	18.32	14.21	2.42	0.57	2.73	0.57

Notes: Multiple household characteristics are detailed for the audio extracted characteristics: sex, education, age and housing regime. Please consult subsection 4.3 for the measurement of the variables specified in all columns.

Table 4 shows results for continuous indicators. First, they show that the verbatim reading score (columns 4-7) is slightly lower for 2020 wave than in 2022 wave, which might also suggest a mode effect. Interviewers might have incentives to shorten up questions when using the telephone since losing respondents is easier under this framework. In addition, this mode effect could also be driven by the lower quality that audio records have in a CATI set up as it was discussed in Sections 5.1 and 5.2. Our results for our verbatim reading score show a positive gradient by education level and a negative gradient by age which implies that when older and less educated respondents are interviewed interviewers tend to deviate more on average from the protocol of verbatim reading. Besides, this dimension remains similar in both waves and across other respondents' characteristics. With respect to silent time (columns 8-11), there is a noticeable difference between waves (30.09 secs vs. 18.32 for the total number of observations). Again, this might be related to the fact that the 2020 wave was fully implemented by telephone so that interviewers could not help respondents when they were using or looking for the specific showcard associated to the question on expectations. Speech rate (columns 12-15) does not vary much either by respondents' characteristics or by wave although somewhat larger numbers are obtained for all groups in the 2020 edition, which could also be associated to the use of the telephone during the interview. Even

though, verbatim reading and speed rates represent two ways of shorten the interview, the length of audio records is on average longer for the 2020 interviews (Table 2), probably as a result of longer silent times.

6.1.2 Measures of uncertainty in house price expectations

One of the main applications for the automatic extraction of measures about the elicitation process from audio records is to analyse how interviewers' behaviour and problems encountered by respondents in the answering process can affect or associated to their responses. One important advantage of asking households probabilistic expectations questions is that this formulation allows them to express uncertainty or risk. There have been different proposals in the recent literature to measure agents' uncertainty from their elicited expectations (Krüger and Pavlova, 2024). one simple form of calculating the uncertainty parametrically can be found in Bover (2015). In such paper, all bins' points are distributed uniformly. Differently, Engelberg et al. (2009) demonstrate that agents beliefs for future events or expectations can be modeled as a generalized Beta distribution. Such assumption implies the use of two parameters to describe the shape of beliefs and two more to give their support^{††}. Besides, this provides a flexible form that permits to have different values for the mean, median, and mode. Figure 2 provides an example of how to compute the subjective probabilistic distribution on house price changes for a specific household using this methodology^{‡‡}.

Applying this methodology to each household, we calculate the interquartile range (IQR) of the fitted distribution, which is a measure of uncertainty. Alternatively, we can also calculate a comparable but non-parametric version of this previous measure using the so-called expectations concentration (EC) index. This index can be written as follows:

$$EC_i = \sum_{j=1}^5 a_{ij}^2 \quad (3)$$

^{††}We assign a support of -15 and +15 for the lower and upper bounds of the top left and right allocation options of the question

^{‡‡}In fact, this methodology is used by the New York FED to compute different measures or moments of the individuals' subjective probabilistic distributions using data from their Consumer of Survey Expectations (Armantier et al., 2017)

Figure 2: Parametric Model of Subjective Probabilistic Expectations

(a) *Notes:* in this example, a specific household allocated points in the following way: (0, 0, 6, 3, 1). The interquartile range (uncertainty) is 3.9. Expectations concentration (EC): 0.325.

EC is calculated for each household i and normalized to a $[0, 1]$ range. This measure captures the degree of concentration of the allocated ten points of the household by taking a value of 1 for the case of exact bunching in one slot, while a value of 0 for an uniform allocation along all possible a answers (2 points to each). The latter corresponds to the less concentrated scenario when a respondent assigns points.

Finally, we also compute as a measure of uncertainty a binary indicator that captures whether the respondent assigns all points to a single slot, which may signal total lack of uncertainty about the house price growth and that we call the bunching indicator.

Table 5 shows some statistics for the different measures of uncertainty that we have just explained across waves and several households and interviewers' characteristics. Regarding household characteristics, the age exhibits a non-linear relationship with uncertainty, where younger respondents show the highest IQR (3.8 in the 2022 wave), while those over 65 display the lowest (2.59). This could reflect life-cycle effects in housing market knowledge and risk perception, but it might also be influenced by a higher tendency of old people to assign points to fewer scenarios because of lack of understanding of the exercise. Educational attainment demonstrates an interesting pattern: tertiary-educated individuals exhibit higher values of uncertainty, while primary-educated respondents show lower uncertainty, although this pattern disappears in 2022. Housing tenure status appears relevant, with non-owners showing higher IQR than owners, potentially indicating greater uncertainty among those not directly participating in the housing market. No noticeable gender differences are

Table 5: Subjective Probabilistic Expectations of Future House Price Changes

		IQR				EC				Bunching	
		EFF2020		EFF2022		EFF2020		EFF2022		EFF2020	EFF2022
		Avg.	Std.	Avg.	Std.	Avg.	Std.	Avg.	Std.	%.	%.
<i>Households</i>											
Age	Under 35	3.32	2.45	3.80	2.67	0.53	0.36	0.48	0.33	0.33	0.24
	35-45	3.66	2.74	3.46	2.52	0.56	0.36	0.54	0.35	0.37	0.33
	46-55	3.40	2.91	3.33	2.73	0.60	0.37	0.58	0.35	0.43	0.38
	56-65	3.04	2.45	3.16	2.61	0.62	0.36	0.62	0.34	0.44	0.41
	66-75	3.14	2.77	2.67	2.35	0.66	0.36	0.68	0.33	0.50	0.49
Gender	Over 75	2.64	2.39	2.59	2.29	0.70	0.34	0.71	0.33	0.53	0.53
	Female	3.19	2.82	3.13	2.63	0.64	0.36	0.63	0.34	0.47	0.42
Education	Male	3.22	2.59	3.15	2.53	0.60	0.36	0.60	0.35	0.42	0.39
	Primary	2.78	2.71	3.18	2.94	0.75	0.33	0.69	0.33	0.61	0.51
Housing Regime	Secondary	3.30	2.97	3.18	2.78	0.65	0.36	0.64	0.35	0.48	0.45
	Tertiary	3.26	2.44	3.11	2.33	0.56	0.36	0.57	0.34	0.37	0.36
Housing Regime	Non-owner	3.32	3.00	3.38	2.83	0.63	0.36	0.63	0.35	0.46	0.43
	Owner	3.19	2.60	3.08	2.50	0.61	0.36	0.61	0.35	0.43	0.40
<i>Interviewers</i>											
Education	Secondary	3.13	2.62	2.93	2.49	0.61	0.36	0.66	0.34	0.42	0.47
	Tertiary	3.25	2.71	3.27	2.62	0.62	0.36	0.58	0.34	0.45	0.37
Experience	Between 5 and 15 y.	3.48	2.80	3.26	2.58	0.57	0.36	0.59	0.35	0.38	0.39
	Less than 5 years	2.94	2.53	3.30	2.52	0.67	0.35	0.58	0.35	0.52	0.37
Gender	More than 15 y.	3.01	2.57	3.03	2.59	0.65	0.36	0.63	0.34	0.48	0.43
	Female	3.13	2.70	3.02	2.54	0.64	0.36	0.64	0.35	0.48	0.44
	Male	3.39	2.62	3.43	2.64	0.56	0.35	0.55	0.34	0.35	0.32
<i>Total</i>											
		3.20	2.68	3.14	2.58	0.618	0.361	0.611	0.345	0.43	0.402

Notes: The table shows three different moments of the households' subjective probabilistic distributions. The first column shows the interquartile range of a fitted generalized Beta distribution, following the methodology of [Engelberg et al. \(2009\)](#) and [Armantier et al. \(2017\)](#). It represents households' uncertainty on future prices of their main residence. The second column shows the expectations concentration, of equation 3, which is just a descriptive statistic with no parametric assumptions of the underlying expectation distribution. Finally, the bunching indicator in the third column indicates whether the household distributed all 10 points to one slot. Note that EFF2020 was made in CATI mode, while EFF2022 in CAPI mode.

observed. Regarding interviewers, a notable experience gradient emerges, where mid-career interviewers (5-15 years) elicit responses with higher IQR compared to both less and more experienced colleagues. Interviewer gender shows substantial differences: male interviewers elicit responses with higher IQR but lower EC compared to female interviewers, suggesting potential interviewer effects on response patterns. Interviewer education level appears to influence responses, with tertiary-educated interviewers eliciting higher IQR values compared to those with secondary education.

6.2 Relating heterogeneity in audio measures to households and interviewers' characteristics

6.2.1 By Household Characteristics

Table 8 in the Appendix presents results for the association between the measures extracted from audio records with households characteristics using multiple regression. In general, results are consistent with the patterns observed for the unconditional means by breakdown shown in the previous Tables 3 and 4. Remarkably, being aged over 75 (as opposed to younger than 35) has a negative significant effect on interviewers reading the question formulation literally and in the reminder of the total score of the exercise, and positive on performing non-neutral probing and providing clarifications. Being male (as opposed to female) is positively associated to verbatim reading but negatively to speech rate, non-neutral probing, lack of understanding, silence time and doubting when trying to understand and come up with an answer. Having tertiary education (as opposed to primary) has a positive and significant effect on verbatim reading, the use of the showcard, receiving the reminder than the points should add up to ten, and a negative and significant effect on the speech rate, non-neutral probing, the occurrence of understanding problems and doubts and the time of silence.

6.2.2 By Interviewer Characteristics

Table 9 in the Appendix presents results from multiple regressions for each audio indicator on interviewers' characteristics. Having tertiary education (as opposed to secondary) is positively associated to mentioning the showcard, giving the reminder, using non-neutral probing, households' expressing lack of understanding and on the amount of silence in the audio. On the other hand, a higher education level is negatively associated with presence of doubts and on the speech rate. Being more experienced exhibits a positive association with giving the reminder about the points to be distributed and on the speech rate, and a negative association on the amount of silence in the audio. Finally, male interviewers seems to be more likely to give the reminder, exhibit higher speech rates and amounts of silence of the conversation, and less likely to read verbatim.

Table 10 in the Appendix show results from multiple regressions for each audio indicator on household and interviewers' characteristics jointly. Coefficients and conclusions remain the same.

6.3 Audio Measures and house price expectations

As we mentioned above, one of the main purpose of the present analysis is to determine to what extent interviewers' behaviour and problems encountered by respondents in the answering process can affect their responses. To do so, we study whether our audio extracted measures are associated to the different indicators of households' uncertainty described in Table 5. Table 6 contains the results from multiple-regressions, which show interesting correlations. For example, we observe that silence duration and reminders to sum to 10 points seem to generate a larger dispersion in the assignment of points when responding to the house price question. In particular, we obtain a positive correlation between both interviewers' behaviours and the IQR (0.515 and 0.452 respectively) while the correlation is negative for the EC indicator (-0.096 and -0.117, respectively) and bunching (-0.742 and -0.814, respectively). This might suggest that these interviewers' behaviors help respondents better understand and think more carefully about the exercise, giving rise to more dispersed answers.

Interviewers' inducement (non-neutral probing) shows differential effects, having no significant impact on the IQR but increasing both EC (0.066) and bunching (0.499). Cognition load indicators reveal that both lack of understanding and the presence of doubts decreases the uncertainty as measured by the the IQR (-0.341 and -0.299) and by the EC (0.069 and 0.045). Higher speech rates are also associated with lower IQR (-0.150) and higher EC (0.049), and bunching (0.274), possibly indicating more rushed responses. The models show varying degrees of fit. Specifically, 40% of the sample variation in the EC of households' responses can be explained with our estimations.

Table 11 in the Appendix shows the extended version of the previous Table including household's and interviewers' characteristics. The associations between uncertainty indicators and audio extracted measures on the elicitation process remain the same once we include

Table 6: Expectations Uncertainty vs. Audio Characteristics

	IQR	EC	Bunching
Verbatim Reading	0.088** (0.035)	-0.022*** (0.004)	-0.118*** (0.018)
Int. shows Card	-0.015 (0.055)	0.007 (0.005)	0.104** (0.053)
Reminder to Sum 10	0.452*** (0.069)	-0.117*** (0.016)	-0.814*** (0.135)
Speech Rate	-0.150** (0.058)	0.049*** (0.005)	0.274*** (0.033)
Induces	-0.091 (0.097)	0.066*** (0.020)	0.499*** (0.128)
Lack of Understanding	-0.341** (0.116)	0.069*** (0.015)	0.162 (0.106)
Doubt	-0.299*** (0.059)	0.045*** (0.008)	0.138 (0.088)
Silence (secs.)	0.515*** (0.038)	-0.096*** (0.006)	-0.742*** (0.074)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>			
Wave	Yes	Yes	Yes
Interviewer	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Fit statistics</i>			
Observations	10,969	10,970	11,383
R ²	0.104	0.267	
Pseudo R ²	0.024	0.410	0.207

Notes: Clustered (Wealth) standard-errors in parentheses. Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1. Household controls are included in this estimation (gender, age, education and wealth strata).

such controls. In addition, the results reveal strong age effects. Older households exhibit systematically different patterns, with those over 75 showing substantially lower IQR (-0.815), while higher EC (0.202) and bunching (1.08) compared to younger cohorts. This age gradient is monotonic and it becomes stronger with age, especially for those above 56. Education levels also play a significant role. Tertiary-educated households show lower EC (-0.081) and bunching (-0.408) compared to those with primary education, suggesting probably that high educated respondents think more carefully and better understand the exercise of assigning points to different scenarios. Housing regime matters as well, with owners displaying lower EC (-0.051) and bunching (-0.291) compared to non-owners, which point to a larger genuine level of uncertainty among those who rent. Interviewer characteristics emerge as important factors as well. Male interviewers elicit responses with higher IQR (0.306) and lower EC (-0.077) and bunching (-0.483) on average, suggesting systematic differences in inter-

viewing practices or styles by gender. Interviewers' experience shows small but significant effects, with more experienced interviewers associated with slightly lower IQR (-0.005) and marginally higher EC (0.0004).

6.3.1 Heterogeneous effects

We can also extend the analysis to different subsamples and analyze to what extent these associations between audio extracted measures and uncertainty indicators are heterogeneous or differ by household type. To do so, we conduct the same analysis as in the previous section using different subsamples. In the case of bunching, log-odds ratios are plotted.

Results in Figure 6 for 'Induces' and 'Lack of Understanding' measures show heterogeneous effects by gender: the correlations between each of these variables and the uncertainty indicators for males are significantly different from those for females. In the case of the 'Speech Rate', the correlation is more similar across genders, though slightly stronger for male respondents for the EC and Bunching measures. We find striking differences by gender in the 'Reminder to Sum 10' effects. While both genders show positive IQR responses to this interviewer behavior, female respondents demonstrate somewhat stronger reactions. For EC and Bunching, these behaviors show negative correlations with uncertainty measures for both genders, but with slightly larger magnitudes for female respondents. 'Verbatim Reading' shows remarkably consistent effects across genders, suggesting this interviewer behavior influences responses similarly in both cases. Conversely, 'Int. shows Card' exhibits some gender heterogeneity, with male respondents showing slightly different response patterns. Overall, gender differences in the correlations of interest are significant in the case of the speech rate, the interviewer showing the card, the non-neutral probing and for the expressing doubts measure.

For the age groups (Figure 7), the IQR panel shows remarkable age gradients for several variables. For example, the 'Lack of Understanding' coefficient reveals a marked pattern, with older respondents (over 65) displaying substantially more negative coefficients compared to middle-aged and younger respondents. The 'Silence' variable demonstrates an opposite gradient, with older respondents showing larger positive coefficients. The EC measure re-

veals more nuanced but systematic differences across age groups. While the coefficients are smaller in magnitude (note the different scale on the x-axis), there are clear patterns in variables like 'Induces' and 'Verbatim Reading' where age appears to correlate with EC at different levels. In the Bunching panel, the positive coefficients found for most audio measures indicate that for all age groups they tend to increase concentration in responses, but with varying intensities. The 'Doubt' and 'Induces' variables show especially pronounced age-related heterogeneity in their effect on concentration.

For the education groups (Figure 8), the IQR panel indicates that the 'Lack of Understanding' variable demonstrates a clear educational gradient, with tertiary-educated respondents showing more negative coefficients compared to those with primary education. The 'Reminder to Sum 10' variable shows an interesting pattern where coefficients for low educated respondents are significantly higher than for higher-educated. This suggests that being reminded by the interviewer about the 10 points affects more respondents' answers in the case of the lower-educated households. The EC measure, while showing smaller coefficients in magnitude (note the x-axis scale from -0.2 to 0.1), reveals subtle but important educational differences. For the 'Speech Rate' variable we find significant differences across education levels, with higher-educated respondents coefficients being larger. The Bunching panel, expressed in log-odds ratios, shows substantial variation across education levels as well. Again, the 'Speech Rate' variable shows again a clear gradient, meaning that the correlation between this variable and the Bunching propensity varies significantly across educational levels.

Lastly, for home owners vs non owners (Figure 9), the IQR panel reveals substantial heterogeneity in response patterns between the two groups. The most pronounced differences emerge in the 'Lack of Understanding' and 'Silence' variables, where for homeowners negative correlations are larger. The EC measure presents more modest differences between the groups, with coefficients generally clustered around zero. However, the precision of these estimates, as evidenced by the narrow confidence intervals, lends credibility to even small differences observed, particularly in the 'Lack of Understanding', 'Speech Rate' and 'Doubt' variables. The systematic variation in these coefficients points to meaningful differences in

how responses in our expectation question by these two groups are affected or are associated to them. The Bunching analysis indicates substantial differences in correlations as well. For example, we find marked differences in the ‘Speech Rate’ and ‘Lack of Understanding’ variables, similarly to results obtained for EC.

7 Conclusion

The utilization of Automatic Speech Recognition tools open a new world of possibilities in the production of survey data, specially for the monitoring of interviewers’ compliance with recommended protocols and respondents’ reactions to questions. As far as we know, this is the first paper that generates transcriptions data from audio records using ML techniques and compute specific measures to assess the incidence of interviewers’ compliance with protocols and respondents’ difficulties. Moreover, this evidence provides new and relevant insights to the literature on the measurement of subjective expectations. Our results, based on audio records from the Spanish Survey of Household Finances, show that the incidence of deviations from protocols such as the verbatim reading of questions and non-neutral probing is non-negligible. Besides, the incidence of respondents asking for clarifications or being reminded that points should be add up to ten is also high. In addition to the heterogeneity of these measures by demographic groups, we also document how they are associated to the different measures of uncertainty computed from households’ responses in the EFF data. In particular, speech rate, verbatim reading and non-neutral probing seem to have substantial effect on the incidence of those responses. Additionally, we find that these associations vary across households, exhibiting a non-negligible level of heterogeneity by age, gender or education level.

These results show the importance of understanding and monitoring the elicitation process to collect accurate and valid data on individuals’ subjective probabilistic expectations. One important advantage of audio records is that they can be collected massively for the whole sample which guarantees the representativeness of the results as opposed to other evaluation methods such as cognitive interviews. In this sense, the most promising application of this work is the design of a tool that can be used during fieldwork to allow data producers and

experts to monitor incidences, misunderstandings or deviations and address them almost immediately.

From a methodological perspective, future work should focus on improving the accuracy of the behavioral coding system used in order to reach levels of granularity similar to that of manually annotated audios. To achieve this, it is essential to improve the algorithms focused on diarization in order to distinguish between the interviewer and the respondent during their interaction. Moreover, a better quality of the audios is needed since, as we have experienced, this is a key factor in Automatic Speech Recognition applications. Finally, developing a faster pipeline is crucial if we want to apply this methodology massively to each entire interview and/or all survey items.

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A Tables

Table 7: Demographic characteristics of DK/NA in total sample

Variables	Observations		DK/NA (%)	
	2020	2022	2020	2022
Female	2549	2726	3.84	6.71
Male	3764	3659	2.39	3.74
Primary	929	802	7.43	12.47
Secondary	2244	2315	2.85	5.70
Tertiary	3090	3220	1.52	2.39
Under 35	342	412	2.05	4.85
35-45	1054	1036	1.14	3.09
46-55	1430	1498	1.47	3.87
56-65	1436	1503	2.16	3.66
66-75	1129	1045	3.90	5.93
Over 75	922	891	7.92	10.44
Non-owner occupiers	1241	1447	4.51	8.02
Owner occupiers	5072	4938	2.60	4.13
Total	6313	6385	2.98	5.01

Notes: Household sample statistics for EFF2020 and EFF2022. Sample is not restricted to those accepting audio recording.

Table 8: Household Characteristics

	Verbatim Reading	Int. shows Card	Reminder to Sum 10	Speech Rate	Induces	Lack of Understanding	Doubt	Silence (secs.)
HH: Male	0.064*** (0.016)	0.013 (0.102)	-0.109 (0.080)	-0.098*** (0.018)	-0.260*** (0.050)	-0.745*** (0.140)	-0.663*** (0.063)	-0.033** (0.014)
HH Age: 35-45	-0.016 (0.038)	0.149 (0.149)	-0.188 (0.192)	0.029 (0.038)	-0.012 (0.087)	-0.124 (0.222)	0.219** (0.110)	0.011 (0.050)
HH Age: 46-55	-0.103*** (0.018)	0.192* (0.106)	-0.274* (0.157)	0.056 (0.037)	0.185 (0.158)	0.048 (0.286)	0.330*** (0.099)	-0.005 (0.057)
HH Age: 56-65	-0.133*** (0.022)	0.229 (0.172)	-0.387** (0.187)	0.081 (0.048)	0.203 (0.183)	0.069 (0.370)	0.578*** (0.096)	-0.031 (0.048)
HH Age: 66-75	-0.284*** (0.032)	0.211 (0.162)	-0.312 (0.214)	0.088 (0.057)	0.493** (0.216)	0.109 (0.332)	0.828*** (0.108)	-0.042 (0.051)
HH Age: Over 75	-0.424*** (0.024)	-0.117 (0.203)	-0.544*** (0.187)	0.043 (0.053)	0.865*** (0.223)	0.306 (0.317)	0.876*** (0.190)	0.078* (0.039)
HH Education: Secondary	0.072*** (0.022)	0.277** (0.110)	0.363*** (0.099)	-0.092*** (0.024)	0.208* (0.107)	-0.612** (0.238)	-0.189* (0.108)	0.075*** (0.021)
HH Education: Tertiary	0.133*** (0.025)	0.365*** (0.086)	0.448*** (0.112)	-0.154*** (0.039)	-0.177 (0.181)	-1.14*** (0.220)	-0.463*** (0.125)	0.033 (0.022)
HH Regime: Owner	0.043* (0.022)	-0.237** (0.105)	0.092* (0.052)	0.039 (0.025)	-0.008 (0.117)	-0.340* (0.193)	-0.230*** (0.084)	-0.110*** (0.032)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>								
Interviewer	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Wave	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Fit statistics</i>								
Observations	11,399	11,286	10,368	11,399	10,925	10,129	11,377	11,399
R ²	0.112			0.352				0.228
Pseudo R ²	0.042	0.115	0.346	0.153	0.091	0.103	0.068	0.091

Clustered (Wealth) standard-errors in parentheses. Wealth strata also included in controls
 Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1

Table 9: Interviewer Characteristics

	Verbatim Reading	Int. shows Card	Reminder to Sum 10	Speech Rate	Induces	Lack of Understanding	Doubt	Silence (secs.)
Int. Education: Tertiary	0.026 (0.015)	0.327*** (0.060)	0.483*** (0.120)	-0.130* (0.059)	0.225*** (0.063)	0.302** (0.131)	-0.121*** (0.041)	0.073** (0.025)
Int. Experience	-0.0007 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.003)	0.020*** (0.003)	0.018*** (0.001)	-0.003 (0.005)	0.0005 (0.006)	0.0009 (0.003)	-0.009*** (0.001)
Int. Sex: Male	-0.150*** (0.028)	-0.101 (0.064)	0.502*** (0.131)	0.344*** (0.064)	-0.054 (0.090)	0.155 (0.133)	0.023 (0.059)	0.110** (0.037)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>								
Wave	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Wealth	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Fit statistics</i>								
Observations	11,465	11,465	11,465	11,465	11,465	11,465	11,465	11,465
R ²	0.010			0.120				0.123
Pseudo R ²	0.004	0.032	0.020	0.045	0.009	0.025	0.017	0.046

Clustered (Wealth) standard-errors in parentheses
 Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1

Table 10: Household & Interviewer Characteristics

	Verbatim Reading	Int. shows Card	Reminder to Sum 10	Speech Rate	Induces	Lack of Understanding	Doubt	Silence (secs.)
Int. Education: Tertiary	0.027 (0.016)	0.347*** (0.061)	0.481*** (0.115)	-0.130* (0.059)	0.220*** (0.067)	0.317** (0.136)	-0.120*** (0.045)	0.073** (0.026)
Int. Experience	-0.001 (0.0010)	-0.002 (0.003)	0.019*** (0.003)	0.018*** (0.001)	-0.003 (0.005)	0.0002 (0.007)	0.002 (0.003)	-0.009*** (0.001)
Int. Sex: Male	-0.162*** (0.029)	-0.124** (0.058)	0.494*** (0.126)	0.351*** (0.066)	-0.030 (0.086)	0.190 (0.137)	0.065 (0.060)	0.109** (0.038)
HH: Male	0.066*** (0.018)	0.025 (0.098)	-0.171*** (0.065)	-0.125*** (0.017)	-0.201*** (0.047)	-0.700*** (0.127)	-0.639*** (0.062)	-0.023* (0.011)
HH Age: 35-45	-0.021 (0.045)	0.145 (0.149)	-0.150 (0.118)	0.059 (0.046)	-0.071 (0.075)	-0.132 (0.172)	0.185* (0.101)	0.003 (0.055)
HH Age: 46-55	-0.096*** (0.025)	0.190* (0.109)	-0.227** (0.105)	0.051 (0.049)	0.135 (0.169)	0.004 (0.242)	0.292*** (0.087)	-0.023 (0.061)
HH Age: 56-65	-0.128*** (0.030)	0.230 (0.170)	-0.309*** (0.106)	0.075 (0.051)	0.154 (0.194)	0.129 (0.322)	0.529*** (0.087)	-0.051 (0.054)
HH Age: 66-75	-0.291*** (0.038)	0.227 (0.164)	-0.093 (0.144)	0.058 (0.060)	0.454* (0.237)	0.169 (0.279)	0.757*** (0.109)	-0.067 (0.059)
HH Age: Over 75	-0.408*** (0.037)	-0.056 (0.214)	-0.228 (0.159)	0.037 (0.060)	0.805*** (0.232)	0.344 (0.269)	0.814*** (0.173)	0.037 (0.051)
HH Education: Secondary	0.070*** (0.021)	0.281*** (0.105)	0.409*** (0.097)	-0.078** (0.032)	0.182** (0.075)	-0.529** (0.260)	-0.184* (0.109)	0.056** (0.024)
HH Education: Tertiary	0.127*** (0.024)	0.378*** (0.090)	0.501*** (0.111)	-0.158*** (0.041)	-0.155 (0.144)	-1.01*** (0.229)	-0.459*** (0.129)	0.021 (0.017)
HH Regime: Owner	0.040 (0.025)	-0.245** (0.100)	0.084 (0.064)	0.043 (0.029)	-0.003 (0.112)	-0.395** (0.185)	-0.225*** (0.083)	-0.110** (0.036)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>								
Wave	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Wealth	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Fit statistics</i>								
Observations	11,399	11,399	11,399	11,399	11,399	11,399	11,399	11,399
R ²	0.030			0.127				0.127
Pseudo R ²	0.011	0.037	0.024	0.048	0.022	0.054	0.047	0.048

Clustered (Wealth) standard-errors in parentheses. Wealth strata also included in controls
 Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1

Table 11: Household & Interviewer Characteristics vs. Expectation

	IQR	IQR	IQR	EC	EC	EC	Bunching	Bunching	Bunching
HH: Male	0.085 (0.063)	0.103 (0.061)	0.097 (0.062)	-0.034*** (0.007)	-0.031*** (0.007)	-0.029*** (0.006)	-0.155** (0.061)	-0.133** (0.055)	-0.121** (0.054)
HH Age: 35-45	0.017 (0.094)	0.027 (0.092)	0.022 (0.098)	0.056*** (0.008)	0.063*** (0.008)	0.063*** (0.009)	0.352*** (0.110)	0.397*** (0.111)	0.395*** (0.119)
HH Age: 46-55	-0.137 (0.089)	-0.119 (0.087)	-0.114 (0.088)	0.094*** (0.011)	0.101*** (0.010)	0.099*** (0.011)	0.602*** (0.114)	0.648*** (0.113)	0.646*** (0.119)
HH Age: 56-65	-0.363*** (0.109)	-0.323** (0.105)	-0.322** (0.109)	0.115*** (0.014)	0.121*** (0.014)	0.120*** (0.014)	0.648*** (0.140)	0.698*** (0.139)	0.692*** (0.143)
HH Age: 66-75	-0.529*** (0.078)	-0.477*** (0.076)	-0.480*** (0.079)	0.163*** (0.011)	0.170*** (0.011)	0.169*** (0.011)	0.951*** (0.110)	1.01*** (0.114)	1.00*** (0.117)
HH Age: Over 75	-0.880*** (0.129)	-0.818*** (0.131)	-0.815*** (0.139)	0.198*** (0.016)	0.205*** (0.015)	0.202*** (0.017)	1.03*** (0.137)	1.09*** (0.141)	1.08*** (0.151)
HH Education: Secondary	-0.032 (0.056)	-0.0004 (0.059)	0.003 (0.060)	-0.022** (0.009)	-0.018* (0.009)	-0.019* (0.009)	-0.042 (0.074)	-0.013 (0.079)	-0.020 (0.074)
HH Education: Tertiary	-0.050 (0.054)	0.035 (0.079)	0.031 (0.085)	-0.094*** (0.007)	-0.083*** (0.008)	-0.081*** (0.008)	-0.488*** (0.076)	-0.412*** (0.085)	-0.408*** (0.078)
HH Regime: Owner	-0.011 (0.056)	0.010 (0.059)	0.006 (0.058)	-0.056*** (0.010)	-0.051*** (0.010)	-0.051*** (0.010)	-0.320*** (0.057)	-0.288*** (0.065)	-0.291*** (0.064)
Int. Education: Tertiary			0.136** (0.059)			-0.010 (0.010)			-0.035 (0.083)
Int. Experience			-0.005* (0.003)			0.0004* (0.0002)			0.003* (0.001)
Int. Sex: Male			0.306*** (0.051)			-0.077*** (0.012)			-0.483*** (0.090)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>									
Wave	Yes								
<i>Fit statistics</i>									
Observations	10,969	10,969	10,969	10,970	10,970	10,970	11,399	11,399	11,399
R ²	0.068	0.070	0.074	0.180	0.183	0.193			
Pseudo R ²	0.015	0.015	0.016	0.261	0.266	0.283	0.118	0.120	0.128

Notes: Clustered (Wealth) standard-errors in parentheses. Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1. Household controls are included in this estimation (gender, age, education and wealth strata). Each second column of each dependant variable (i.e., columns 2, 5 and 8) add wealth strata controls.

B Figures

B.1 Methods

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Figure 3: Pipeline Map

Notes: Figure shows the scheme that we have employed to go from the raw audios to the final transcriptions and VAD timestamps used to compute the different measures of interest.

‡The transcriptions and VAD utilized in the feature engineering step depends on the selected transcription as explained in Section 4.2.1

Figure 4: Output of Manually Annotated Audio with Audacity

Notes: Figure shows the manually annotated voice activity detected areas in an audio of our sample.

Figure 5: Output of Pyannote Annotated Audio

Notes: Figure shows the automatically annotated voice activity detected areas in an audio of our sample.

B.2 Results

Figure 6: Gender Heterogeneity

Figure 7: Age Heterogeneity

Figure 8: Education Heterogeneity

Figure 9: Ownership Heterogeneity

C Behavioural codes and their expressions

Table 12 includes the regular expressions that have been searched in the transcription of the audios to establish the presence of a particular behaviour. In some of the expressions, the accented and unaccented versions have been included as Whisper may have generated both.

Table 13 contains the explanations of the variables computed and some examples that can be useful to understand them.

Table 12: Regular expressions used to search in the audios transcriptions

Variables	Regex Pattern
Reminder to Sum 10	(?:sumar 10), (?:total 10), (?:sumar diez), (?:total diez)
Int. shows Card	(?:cartón), (?:Cartón), (?:carton), (?:Carton)
Doubt	(?:no lo sé), (?:no sé), (?:No lo sé), (?:No sé), (?:que se yo), (?:Que sé yo), (?:ni idea), (?:Ni idea)
Lack of Understanding	(?:no lo entiendo), (?:no entiendo), (?:No lo entiendo), (?:No entiendo)
Induce	(?:Entonces\b[^\.]*?\bpongo\b\?.?), (?:entonces\b[^\.]*?\bpongo\b\?.?), (?:Entonces\b[^\.]*?\bponemos\b\?.?), (?:entonces\b[^\.]*?\bponemos\b\?.?), (?:Entonces\b[^\.]*?\bpondría\b\?.?), (?:entonces\b[^\.]*?\bpondría\b\?.?), (?:Ponemos\b[^\.]*?\bentonces\b\?.?), (?:ponemos\b[^\.]*?\bentonces\b\?.?), (?:Pongo\b[^\.]*?\bentonces\b\?.?), (?:pongo\b[^\.]*?\bentonces\b\?.?), (?:Pondría\b[^\.]*?\bentonces\b\?.?), (?:pondría\b[^\.]*?\bentonces\b\?.?)

Table 13: Explanation features

Features	Description	Fragments of Real Examples
Regular Expression Based		
Int. shows Card	The transcript contains indications to the showcard	<i>No. Mira, mirando el cartón 10, estamos interesados en conocer cómo cree usted que evolucionará el valor de su vivienda en los próximos 12 meses. Al final tiene que sumar diez y lo puede repartir como quiera.</i>
Reminder to Sum 10	The transcript contains clarifications to the respondent that the points allocated have to sum 10.	
Induce	The answer is guided in a non-neutral way	Vale, entonces , ¿qué hago? ¿ Pongo los 10 en estable o pongo los 10 en estable?
Doubt	The transcript contains statements indicating doubt	No sé , yo creo que estará estable, pero no sé cómo repartir esto
Lack of Understanding	The transcript contains statements indicating lack of understanding	¿Aquí cuántos ponemos? Es que no entiendo si es lo que quieres decir.
Computed Features		
Verbatim Reading	Score that captures the semantic similarity between the wording of the question and the transcribed text of the first 30 seconds of the audio	
Speech rate	Number of words in the transcript divided by the total duration of the audio	
Silence time	Total duration time of silence in seconds in the audio	

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Example 1: Complete transcription of an audio that contains a mention to the showcard an a reminder of the total sum and a non-neutral probing expression: *‘Estamos interesados en conocer cómo crees que evolucionará el valor de vuestra vivienda en los próximos 12 meses. Reparte por favor 10 puntos entre las 5 posibilidades del **cartón** 10. ¿Te traigo un bol? No, no, no. Si quieres escribir puedes. Asignando más puntos a lo que creas más probable. Y si alguna te parece imposible le darías cero. O sea, entre otras tiene que **sumar diez** puntos. Yo creo que estable. ¿Darías los diez puntos a estable? A estable. Vale. Yo creo que la subida de más del seis por ciento, cero. De subir, no. ¿Entonces ha bajado? creo que la subida de más del 6% cero. Y la caída no, yo tampoco creo que caiga. Y lo otro, el término medio. Los otros dos, el término medio. Vale, **entonces, ¿qué hago? ¿Pongo** los 10 en estable o pongo los 10 en estable? Sí, no, los demás... Ah, vale, las 10 a repartir. No, no, pues los 10 en esta si no los demás ah vale son 10 a repartir no no pues los 10 en esta los 10 si yo no creo que haya cambios muy sustanciales tal y como están las cosas tenéis previsto mudaros de casa los próximos dos años ni de coña vamos o nos tocan’*

Example 2: Complete transcription of an audio that contains an expression of doubt and lack of understanding: *“Con el cartón número 10 estamos interesados en conocer cómo cree que evolucionará el valor de la vivienda en los próximos 12 meses. Tiene que repartir 10 puntos entre las 5 posibilidades siguientes asignando más puntos a las que crea más probable o 0 si alguna le parece imposible. Yo creo que sé aproximadamente estable, diría yo. ¿Aquí cuántos ponemos? Es que **no entiendo** si es lo que quieres decir. Tiene diez puntos, puede poner poner 2-2-2-2 o 5-5 o 1-5-3, yo qué sé. Repartir en lo que se crea. **No sé**, yo creo que estará estable, pero **no sé** cómo repartir esto, lo puede poner todo aquí también, si cree que no subirá más del 2 y del 6 los 10 puntos aquí vale, ¿tienen previsto mudarse de casa en los próximos dos años?”*